

Detergents are more harmful than COVID 19: Escaping or destruction of Chloroplasts and chlorophylls and methylation

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Abstract:

These days, because of COVID 19, people are using detergents and other washing matters extensively. However, these chemical matters are more harmful than viruses. Previously, the role of detergents in extracting biological proteins has been known. Inspire of this, the usage of this matter in human's life not only don't forbidden but was advised. To warn people, we have done a simple experiment and then design a model to describe results. We have applied detergents on cucumber leaves and expose them to electromagnetic waves. We have observed that a part of leaves lost their green color and other part obtained dark color. After a weak, white part of leaves gain green spots. We have repeated experiment for transgenic oil and observed some dark strains/spots. To describe these events, we propose a model. In our model, molecules of detergents interact with waves and divide to charged atoms like Na^+ and also some groups of CH_3 . Also, molecules of membranes like phospholipids, sulfolipids and galactolipid interact with waves and detergents and divide in to charged ions like P^- , O^- and methyl groups like CH_3 . Consequently, some new molecules are emerged and the structure of membranes could be destroyed. After that, some CH_3 s may combine with some bases of DNAs, active or turn off genes or cause to mutations and cancer. Also, some charged atoms of detergents may force on charged atoms within the membrane of chloroplasts and cause to their migrations from one cell to other. Maybe, this be one of reasons that some parts of leaves are white and some parts are dark. The same events could be observed in human skin cells too. Other reason for changing color of leaves exposing to detergent and waves may be the productions of new molecules by exchanging charged atoms between detergents and chlorophylls and destruction of photosystems.

Keywords: Detergent, leaf, Cancer, Methyl, DNA, Chloroplast, Migration

I.Introduction:

Newly, COVID19 have changed the life of human and causes to an increase in using detergents and different types of washing matters. However, these chemical elements themselves are more harmful and may lead to cancer or different type of diseases. Up to date, many investigations have been done to consider the harm effects of detergents and reduce them. For example, in some researches , it has been discussed that chemical matters like those used in detergents may lead to vision loss in some countries and cause to many other problems [1]. Their experiments have showed that young children may be at especially high risk of experiencing these injuries [2]. According to these studies, using laundry detergent pods, which are dissolvable pouches, has caused to an increase in associated injuries among children [3,4]. In other paper, by using gamma-ray spectrometry (HPGe), it has been shown that some detergent powders have radionuclides more than the recommended limits [5]. In other article, it has been argued that despite the necessity of using detergents to protect public health, the improper disposal of their toxic sewage could present problems. According to this research, phosphates in some detergent formulations increase the population of organisms and as a result, dissolved oxygen depletion in the water reservoirs would occur due to their activities and eutrophication phenomenon [6]. In another investigation, authors have disclosed that that exposure to laundry detergent pods is more dangerous than exposure to traditional detergents. They have discussed that in Italy, 4 months after the introduction of opaque outer packaging by a major company, product-specific exposure rates decreased sharply, suggesting that reducing visibility of laundry detergent pods may be an effective preventive measure [7].

Besides these considerations, many investigators have discussed the methods to use of detergents for extracting biological proteins in cell membranes [8-11]. This means that the role of detergents in destruction of cell membrane and proteins of life has been known. Now, the question arises that does detergents cause to migrations of chloroplasts [12], mitochondria and also emergency of cancer? To response this question, we consider the effects of detergents on the evolutions of plant cells in leaves and propose a mechanism for migration of chloroplasts from cells.

The outline of paper is as follows. In section II, we consider the material and method. In section III, we propose the results of experiments. In section IV, we

propose a model to consider the effects of detergent on the cells. The last section is devoted to conclusion

II. Material and Method:

A. Material:

In this research, we need to below materials:

1. Two types of detergents: A. Anionic detergents, B. Cationic detergents

2. Cucumber leaves

3. Electromagnetic waves

4. Transgenic vegetable oil

5. A camera

6. Water

B. Method:

1. Divide cucumber leaves into four groups.

2. Apply some detergents on two groups.

3. Expose one handle to electromagnetic waves (For example sun rays) and place the other handle in a protected place.

4. After twenty-four hours, we compare them.

5. Apply some transgenic vegetable oil on two other groups.

6. Again, expose one group to electromagnetic waves and place the other group in a protected place.

7. After twenty-four hours, we compare them.

8. After a week, consider the evolutions of plant cells on the leaves in four groups.

IV: Results:

1. Leaves (Applying detergents) which are exposed to electromagnetic waves, lost their green lights after 24 h (See Figure 1).
2. Around the white parts of some of these leaves , some dark spots could be observed.
3. Leaves which aren't exposed to electromagnetic waves, change minorly (See Figure 2).
4. Leaves (Applying transgenic vegetable oil) include some bold stains and spots after 24h (See Figure 3).
5. After one week, it seems that some migrations of chlorophylls from green part to white part occurs (See figure 4)

Fig 1. Leaves (Applying detergents) after 24h.

Figure 2: Leaves which aren't exposed to electromagnetic waves

Fig 3. Leaves (Applying transgenic vegetable oil)

Fig 4. Leaves (Applying detergents) after one week

IV. Discussion

Our results show that detergents cause that first leaves lose their green color in some parts and obtain dark green spots in some other parts. Also, after a week, it seems that eventually, white parts gain their green colors again. However, because of non-normal conditions, they lost water and may dead. To describe these events, we suggest below mechanism:

1. Detergent's molecules interact with molecules of membranes around cells, Chloroplasts and thylakoid and produce new chemical molecules. Molecules of detergents include charged atoms like positive Na^+ and negative oxygen and other negative ions. Also, membranes include phospholipid, sulfolipid, galactolipid. These molecules charged atoms. Consequently, charged atoms of detergents interact with charged atoms of membranes and destroy their structures (See Figure 5).
2. Chlorophylls and detergents could interact with each other, exchange charged atoms and produce new molecules. This causes that chlorophylls lose their properties and couldn't contribute in the process of photosynthesis (See Figure 6).
3. Detergents and molecules in membranes like phospholipids, sulfolipid, galactolipid and other lipids are build from various numbers of CH_3 or combinations of carbon and hydrogen. When they interact with each other and wave, some CH_3 s become free and interact with bases like cytosine in DNAs. By connecting these methyls to DNAs, some of genes may be active or turn off or some mutations occur. This may be the main reason of cancer. It seems that some dark spots on leaves in our experiment be due to methylations (See figure 7).
4. In some conditions, detergents interact with electromagnetic waves and divide into charges atoms. These charges destroy cell membranes, force on the surface of chloroplasts and lead them into out of cells. Then, these chloroplasts are absorbed by other cells. This could be a reason for white color of some parts and dark color of other parts of leaves (See figure 8).

Fig 5. Detergents destroy membranes in plant cells, chloroplasts and Thylakoid.

Sodium Alkyl Sulphate
(Detergent)

→ New Molecules

Detergent + Chlorophyll → Mg[A] + Na [B]

→ The end of photosynthesis

Fig 6: Detergents combine with Chlorophylls and exchange charged atoms and ions

Fig7. Detergets interact with membranes and waves and some CH_3 and other members of methylation groups are emerged. CH_3 may cause to mutation and cancer.

Fig 8. Detergets destroy membranes and cause to escape of chloroplasts from a cell to another one.

Conclusions:

Detergents are harmful chemical matters that have direct effects on human, animal and plant cells. To observe their powers in vanishing life, it is sufficient that you rub a type of detergent on the leaves and expose them in front of electromagnetic waves of the sun. After 24 h, a part of them become white and some parts gain dark color. Also, after a weak, white parts re-obtain the green color. To describe these events, one can show that molecules of detergents include charged atoms and CH_3 . Also, molecules of cell plants including phospholipids, sulfolipids and other matters contain charged atoms and CH_3 . When molecules of detergents interact with membranes, destroy them and induce charged atoms and CH_3 within cells. CH_3 may cause to methylations, mutations and cancer. On the other hand, charged atoms of detergents may force in to chloroplasts and cause to their migrations from a cell to another. We suggest to consider this main problem in human life.

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